

Nephroblastoma in Domestic Animals

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Abstract

Nephroblastomas, also called Wilm's tumor, embryonal nephromas and adenosarcomas is a congenital neoplasm arising from metanephric blastema or its primordium during pre- or post-natal life. Grossly, nephroblastoma may be unilateral or bilateral encapsulated mass of growth which may be single or multiple having variable size some even occupying a large part of the affected kidney. It is characterized by the presence of great structural and histological diversity including blastemal, epithelial and stromal cells. Epithelial elements predominate in these tumors in swine, whereas connective tissue is the major element of the bovine tumors.

Key words: Blastemal, Gross pathology, Nephroblastoma, Triphasic.

INTRODUCTION

Nephroblastomas are also called embryonal nephromas and adenosarcomas because of their morphological variations. The term 'Wilm's tumor' is often applied in human pathology. They are thought to arise from the metanephros or its primordium (Walker, 1943; Moulton, 1961). Nephroblastomas may contain a great variety of tissue types, including generalized spindle cell, sarcomatous, adenomatous, and carcinomatous elements as well as smooth muscle, fat, cartilage, bone, and striated muscle. Nephroblastomas are sometimes considered to be organoid teratomas (Walker, 1943). Epithelial elements predominate in these tumors in swine, whereas connective tissue is the major element of the bovine tumors (Moulton, 1961).

SPECIES AFFECTED

Nephroblastomas are relatively rare in domestic animals but are found most frequently in pigs and chickens (Feldman, 1930; Sullivan and Anderson, 1959; Moulton, 1961). The tumor has also been found in the dog, horse, ox, sheep, and rabbit, but is practically non-existent in the cat (Feldman, 1933; Monlux et al., 1956;

Moulton, 1961). Almost all bovine cases reported are in calves or foetuses (Walker, 1943; Kirkbride and Bicknell, 1972; Misdrop, 2002) with few in adult cattle. They are unilateral, solitary and huge masses and rarely metastasize (Kirkbride and Bicknell, 1972).

PATHOLOGY

Grossly, nephroblastoma may be unilateral or bilateral encapsulated mass of growth which may be single or multiple having variable size some even occupying a large part of the affected kidney (Behera et al., 2021). Microscopic examination of the tissue sections revealed blastemal, epithelial and mesenchymal elements. The blastemal cells were differentiated to form dense, irregular masses, clusters and nests. These cells were round to oval in shape with scanty cytoplasm. The nuclei were spherical, sometimes vesicular and hyperchromatic, containing finely granular chromatin with multiple nucleoli and mitotic figures (Madheswaran et al., 2014). The blastemal cells were arranged into glomeruli and tubular structures lined by flattened epithelium. Some tubules were dilated with eosinophilic fluid and cell debris. Abortive tubules were noticed in most of the tissue

sections. The epithelial cell structures appeared to be the early stages of tubule-glomerulogenesis. The mesenchymal cells were polyhedral in shape, found between tubules (Ramadevi et al., 2011).

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